

Synthesis of Enantioenriched Amines by Iron-Catalysed Amination of Alcohols Employing at Least One Achiral Substrate

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Dedicated to Prof. P. H. Dixneuf for his creative contributions in the field of Fe-catalysis

Received: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Supporting information for this article is available on the WWW under <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/adsc.201#####>.

Abstract. The synthesis of a broad range of enantioenriched amines by the direct Fe-catalysed coupling of amines with alcohols through the borrowing hydrogen strategy, while at least one of these substrates is achiral is reported. When starting from α -chiral amines and achiral alcohols, a wide range of enantioenriched amine products, including *N*-heterocyclic moieties can be obtained with complete retention of stereochemistry and the

power of this method is demonstrated in the one-step synthesis of known pharmaceuticals from commercially available, simple enantiopure primary amines and achiral alcohols. It was also found that the use of β -branched enantioenriched primary alcohols and achiral amines as reaction partners leads to a partial loss of stereochemical integrity in the final product, however, a systematic optimization enabled partial retention of enantiopurity and possible parameters effecting for racemization were identified.

Keywords: amination; borrowing hydrogen strategy; enantioenriched amines; homogeneous catalysis; iron catalysis

Introduction

Enantiopure amines, particularly α -chiral amines, are key structural scaffolds in pharmaceuticals and biologically active compounds, therefore the development of sustainable methods to access these moieties is of prime importance in catalysis research (**Scheme 1A**).^[1] The direct coupling of alcohols with amines *via* the ‘hydrogen borrowing’ methodology^[2] has proven a highly efficient approach for the synthesis of diverse amine products. This approach generates water as the sole by-product, may utilize potentially biomass-derived alcohol substrates^[3], and could also be performed applying non-noble metal catalysts.^[4] However, despite remarkable progress in this field, the development of enantioselective catalytic systems for the *N*-alkylation of amines with alcohols, that might be compatible with the hydrogen-transfer nature of this method, has proven challenging and is currently under development (**Scheme 1B**).^[5]

Apart from introducing chirality during distinct steps in the hydrogen borrowing sequence by enantiopure auxiliaries^[6], catalyst^[7] or ligands^[8],

Scheme 1 A: Selected examples of pharmaceutically relevant α - (first row) and β -chiral (second row) amines; **B:** Schematic approach to the synthesis of chiral amines from enantiopure amine or alcohol precursors *via* iron catalysis. this method also offers the possibility of constructing chiral amines of higher structural complexity by judicious selection of simple, available optically active amines and/or alcohols as starting materials, *provided that no racemization occurs*. Indeed, racemization of imines is a serious challenge, and this phenomenon is also industrially exploited by the formation of imines from chiral amines and benzaldehyde to facilitate racemization *via* the formed azaenolates.^[9]

The above-mentioned approach has been recognized as attractive by multiple groups: Fujita reported the *N*-alkylation of chiral amines with achiral alcohols catalysed by $[\text{Cp}^*\text{IrCl}_2]_2$ ^[10]; examples of optically active amine substrates were employed by Williams^[11]; and our group demonstrated the *N*-alkylation of unprotected amino acids with full retention of stereochemistry using achiral ruthenium-based catalysts^[12]. Recently, Hultsch^[13] described the first example of using a PN^3 manganese pincer complex for the synthesis of cinacalcet through the direct coupling of enantiopure naphthyl substituted amine with 3-(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propan-1-ol. Generally, while retention of chirality was observed with chiral amines, racemization was prevalent when chiral alcohols were used as coupling partner with Ru and Ir based systems.^[11, 14] Very recently Donohoe^[14d] has disclosed an elegant iridium-catalysed annulation strategy for the stereocontrolled synthesis of substituted saturated aza-heterocycles and observed partial racemization when β -chiral alcohols were used as substrates.

Herein we report on the construction of a wide variety of chiral amines, including *N*-heterocyclic derivatives, and pharmacologically active compounds, using a homogeneous catalyst based on non-noble metal Fe and investigate the causes of racemization when enantiopure amines *versus* alcohols are used as coupling partners.

Results and Discussion

We have earlier reported on the use of Knölker's complex (**C1**) in the Fe-catalysed *N*-alkylation of amines with alcohols.^[15] Herein, with the aim to access chiral amine products, we examined the reaction of (*R*)-phenylethylamine ((*R*)-PEA, **2a**) with 1-pentanol (**1a**) to generate chiral amine **3a** using this method. The initially applied reaction conditions with 2 equivalents of 1-pentanol (**1a**) and 6 mol% of **C1** and Me_3NO , at 135 °C in toluene resulted in 62% of pentyl amine and 29% of the corresponding imine. Increasing the amount of alcohol to 4 equivalents, an excellent 88% isolated yield of the desired amine **3a** was obtained without any loss of enantiopurity (chiral HPLC analysis, see SI).

In further studies, the scope and limitations of the newly established Fe-catalysed methodology were investigated. A large variety of enantiopure benzylamines and aliphatic amines were successfully converted into the corresponding chiral *N*-pentyl substituted amines with good to excellent yield, with complete retention of stereochemistry. Benzylamines with various *meta*-substituents afforded excellent isolated yields of the target products regardless of the nature of the substituent (**Scheme 2, 3b-3d**, 81-86%). *Para*-substituted *N*-alkylated phenylethylamines (**3e-3g**) were obtained in 62-90% isolated yields, among them using *p*-fluorobenzylamine as substrate gave the highest product yield (**3g**, 90%). In the latter case, the reaction time was shortened to 8 h without significant change in yield (86% yield after 8 h vs 90% yield after 24 h, 98% *ee* in both cases). Furthermore, sterically hindered chiral amines (**3h, 3i**) were smoothly converted to the desired products (87% and 79% yield, respectively). Various exocyclic amines with a benzylic chiral centre maintained their optical activity (**3j, 3k**); albeit slightly lower yields were obtained due to the minor formation of *N,N*-dialkylated amines. Moderate yields were detected employing enantiopure aliphatic α -branched amines (**3l, 3m**): in these cases, the formation of minor amounts of the double *N*-alkylated products (15-25%) was observed as well (for more details, see SI, **Supplementary Table 1**).

Scheme 2: *N*-Alkylation of α -chiral amines with 1-pentanol. General reaction conditions: amine **2**, 0.5 mmol, 1-pentanol (**1a**, 2 mmol), toluene (2 mL), **C1** (6 mol%), Me₃NO (6 mol%), 135 °C, 24 h. Isolated yields are shown. ^a Results after 8 h reaction time are reported in parenthesis. ^b 10 mol% Ni(OTf)₂ was used.

Next, aiming to obtain chiral tertiary amines, we investigated the effect of Lewis acid additives that can be expected to enhance catalytic activity and *N*-alkylation. Previously, Zhao et.al. demonstrated that Lewis acids (up to 40 mol%) could improve the catalytic activity of **C1**^[16], in the – otherwise sluggish – amination of secondary alcohols. In our hands, the addition of only 10 mol% Ni(OTf)₂, directed the reaction to the formation of *N,N*-dialkylated compounds (**3n**, **3o**) without loss of enantiopurity. This could be attributed to the configurational stability of the chiral iminium intermediate, formed in the second alkylation step (see also **Scheme 6**).

To further expand the scope of the reaction, we turned our attention to the *N*-alkylation of (*R*)-*p*-fluorophenylethylamine (**2g**) with potentially biomass-derived terminal diols, leading to the formation of four-, five- and six-membered *N*-heterocycles in good to excellent isolated yields (68–90%, **5a–5c**, **Scheme 3**) without the loss of stereochemical integrity. However, besides the target product, a minor amount of the corresponding lactone was detected, the latter likely originated from mono-dehydrogenation of the diol, followed by intramolecular hemiacetal formation and its subsequent dehydrogenation^[17]. Other diols such as 3-methylpentane-1,5-diol (**4d**) and 2,2'-

biphenyldimethanol (**4e**) furnished the desired products in 79% and 33% yields, respectively. The yield of the azepane derivative (**5e**) could be significantly improved to 80% by adding 10 mol% Ni(OTf)₂ as was discussed above.

Further investigations related to the scope of the reactions included the use of diverse aliphatic alcohols such as methanol, ethanol, or cinnamyl alcohol as well as a chiral diol as a coupling partner to benzylamine substrates, with moderate success (see Supplementary Information, **Supplementary Table 2**). Good functional group tolerance was demonstrated using *p*-nitrobenzyl alcohol (SI, **Supplementary Table 2**, entry 5). Moreover, a reaction between the aliphatic pentyl amine and a chiral alcohol could be successfully performed, further extending the reaction scope.

Scheme 3: Scope of *N*-heterocycles obtained through the reaction between *p*-fluorophenylethylamine and selected diols. General reaction conditions: 0.5 mmol (**R**)-**2g**, 1 mmol **4**, 2 mL toluene, **C1** (6 mol%), Me₃NO (6 mol%), 135 °C, 24 h. Isolated yields are shown. ^a 10 mol% Ni(OTf)₂ was used.

Next, in order to demonstrate the power and utility of this methodology, we focused on the one-step synthesis of pharmacologically relevant compounds starting from simpler commercially available chiral amines and appropriate alcohol precursors, using the Fe-based Knölker's complex (**Scheme 4**). (*R*)-Fendiline is Ca-channel blocker^[18,19] that is used for the treatment of hypertension and coronary heart disease. Remarkably, employing our optimized Fe-catalyzed protocol, (*R*)-Fendiline could be afforded in 81% yield and 99% ee (**Scheme 4**, left) in one step by directly coupling (*R*)-1-phenylethylamine and 3,3-diphenylpropan-1-ol, which are both commercially available. The amine precursor could be also obtained by asymmetric reductive amination of acetophenone with ammonia or its salts in presence of the ruthenium/C₃-TunePhos catalytic system.^[20] The alcohol can be potentially synthesised through selective palladium-catalysed hydrogenation of 3,3-diphenylallyl alcohol.^[21]

One of the elegant early examples of utilizing hydrogen borrowing methods in the pharmaceutical industry was the preparation of the calcimimetic agent (*R*)-Cinacalcet^[22] by Zentiva (**Scheme 4**, right), using

an iridium catalyst^[23]. Applying our method, this synthesis was successfully carried out with the iron-catalyst **C1** and (*R*)-Cinacalcet was obtained in good isolated yield and excellent enantiopurity, offering a viable non-noble metal-based alternative.

Scheme 4: The enantiopure amine drugs synthesized using the Fe-based catalytic protocol (6 mol% **C1**, 6 mol% Me₃NO, 0.5 mmol amine, 1.5 mmol alcohol, 2 mL toluene, 135 °C, 24 h). Isolated yields are shown. The amine and the alcohol moieties are represented in black and blue, respectively.

In order to determine whether racemization would occur when a chiral alcohol is used as substrate, we examined the model reaction between (*S*)-2-methylbutanol (**1b**) and *p*-anisidine (**6a**). This resulted in a mixture of β -chiral amine **7a** (37%) and a substantial amount of the corresponding imine **8a**

(37%). Solvent screening has not proven beneficial (**Table 1**, entries 1-4). The use of Ni(OTf)₂ and molecular sieves as acidic additives improved this conversion (entries 6 and 7), however also caused major racemization of the amine product. Under neat reaction conditions, amine selectivity increased to 68% (entry 5) and increasing the catalyst loading to 10 mol% in toluene, the desired amine was obtained with 63% isolated yield and 80% *ee* (entry 8). Notably, a significant improvement in terms of enantiopurity was achieved (80% *ee* with **C1** – entry 8 vs 96% *ee* with **C2** – entry 9) when the acetonitrile complex **C2** that does not require activation with Me₃NO was used instead of Fe-catalyst **C1**, suggesting a possible role of this oxidizing agent or the formed Me₃N in racemization.

Further, the scope of the reaction was extended by examining various anilines as coupling partners to (*S*)-2-methylbutanol (**1b**) (**Scheme 5**). With anilines bearing electron-donating substituents (**6a-b**), including those with bulky groups (**6c**), moderate to good isolated product yields with high enantiopurity were achieved (**7a-c**, 42-71%, 80-94% *ee*), whereas electron-withdrawing substituents (**6e**) have shown a deleterious effect on both amine selectivity and enantiomeric excess (**7e**, 38%, 76% *ee*).

Table 1: *N*-Alkylation of *p*-anisidine (**6a**) with (*S*)-2-methylbutanol (**1b**) under various reaction conditions.

Entry	Solvent	Temp., °C	Cat., mol%	Additive, mol%	Conv., %	7a ^a , %	8a ^a , %	<i>ee</i> ^b , %
1	Toluene	135	C1 (6), Me ₃ NO (6)	-	74	37	37	84
2	CPME	135	C1 (6), Me ₃ NO (6)	-	60	24	36	70
3	Octane	135	C1 (6), Me ₃ NO (6)	-	60	30	30	74
4	1,4-Dioxane	135	C1 (6), Me ₃ NO (6)	-	42	11	31	46
5 ^c	-	135	C1 (6), Me ₃ NO (6)	-	85	68	17	76
6	Toluene	135	C1 (6), Me ₃ NO (6)	Ni(OTf) ₂ (10)	99	90	9	6
7	Toluene	135	C1 (6), Me ₃ NO (6)	Mol. sieves	75	48	27	18
8	Toluene	135	C1 (10), Me ₃ NO (10)	-	93	65 (63)	28	80
9	Toluene	135	C2 (10)	-	91	60 (54)	31	96
10	Toluene	130	C2 (10)	-	86	72	14	96
11	Toluene	140	C2 (10)	-	96	55	41	96

General reaction conditions: **6a** (0.25 mmol), (*S*)-**1b** (1 mmol), **C1** (6 mol%), Me₃NO (6 mol%), solvent (1 mL), 135 °C, 24 h. ^a) Determined by GC-FID. ^b) Determined by chiral HPLC. ^c) Neat (*S*)-2-methylbutanol (**1b**) was used. Isolated yields are in parenthesis.

Aniline **6d** afforded the corresponding *N*-alkylated amine **7d** in moderate yield with almost full retention of the stereochemistry in the alcohol coupling partner. Interestingly, 4-hydroxyaniline (**6f**) delivered a target amine product in good yield, however, almost full racemization at the stereogenic centre was observed (**7f**, 68%, 20% *ee*).

Employing other β -branched chiral primary alcohols, the corresponding amines (**7h-i**) were obtained with moderate isolated yields and good

enantiopurity. Notably, applying **C2** as a catalyst, the yields obtained were comparable to those previously obtained with **C1**, whereas the enantiomeric ratios were significantly higher as earlier noted (**7a**, 63%, 80% *ee* vs 54%, 96% *ee*).

In order to rationalize the obtained experimental data, plausible racemization pathways during the formation of the target chiral amine products synthesized from either chiral amine or alcohol are summarized in **Scheme 6**. In the case of *N*-alkylation

of α -chiral amines with achiral aliphatic alcohols, complete retention of enantiopurity was observed in the target amine products (**Scheme 6A**). This allows to rule out pathways potentially responsible for the loss of stereochemistry with these substrates, namely amine to imine dehydrogenation (**III** to **IIIa**)^[24] and isomerization of the chiral imine (**IVa** to **IVb**) formed through the condensation reaction between the carbonyl compound **IIa** and amine **III**. On the other hand, in the reaction between optically active alcohols and anilines (**Scheme 6B**), racemization occurred, which could be triggered either by the tautomerization of the formed chiral aldehyde (**IIa** to **IIb**)^[25], or imine intermediate (**IVa** to **IVb**)^[8,14d] and/or amine to imine dehydrogenation (**V** to **IVa**).

Scheme 5: The *N*-alkylation of anilines with β -chiral alcohols. General reaction conditions: **6** (0.25 mmol), **1** (1 mmol), **C1** (10 mol%), Me₃NO (10 mol%), solvent (1 mL), 135 °C, 24 h. Isolated yields and enantiomeric ratios are reported. ^a Using **C2** (10 mol%).

Aiming to shed light on the specific pathways responsible for the loss of chirality, isomerization of the chiral imine intermediate (**Scheme 6B**, **IVa**), and the possible dehydrogenation of the target amine product (**Scheme 6B**, **V**) were studied.

After the completion of the coupling reaction between *p*-anisidine (**6a**) with (*S*)-2-methylbutanol (**1b**) (**Table 1**, entry 1) sodium borohydride was added to the crude mixture of corresponding amine (**7a**) and imine (**8a**) products and the mixture was heated for 24 h at 135 °C; however, no changes in the enantiomeric ratio were detected. Furthermore, heating of the isolated amine product **7a** in the presence of **C1** and Me₃NO in toluene at 135 °C for 24 h did not cause any racemization either, suggesting that the amine to imine dehydrogenation (**V** to **IVa**) route is not likely. With regard to racemization *via* the imine-enamine tautomerization (**IVa** to **IVb**), we investigated the

reaction between *p*-anisidine (**6a**) with (*S*)-2-methylbutyraldehyde in toluene at 135 °C for 4 hours with and without molecular sieves, respectively, and determined the optical purity of the formed imine (Supplementary Note 3). Significant imine racemization was observed in the presence of molecular sieves, while moderate racemization was observed in their absence. This may be due to the existence of the imine-enamine equilibrium, or could also originate from the configurational lability of the starting aldehyde. When samples from such experiments were analysed at room temperature by ¹H NMR spectroscopy, enamine signals could not be confirmed under these conditions, however we cannot exclude this racemization pathway (see SI, Supplementary Note 1).

When the analogous ¹H NMR experiments were performed by heating separately synthesised (*S*)-2-methylbutyraldehyde^[26] alone, in toluene at 135 °C for 6 hours with and without molecular sieves or Me₃NO, these experiments clearly revealed the corresponding aldehyde/enol equilibrium (**IIa** to **IIb** tautomerization took place) (see SI, Supplementary Note 2) in the presence of both the studied additives.

The contribution of the *in situ* formed chiral aldehyde on the racemization process (**Scheme 6B**, **IIa**) was further evaluated by heating (*S*)-2-methylbutanol and **C1** in presence of Me₃NO, which generated a small amount of (*S*)-2-methylbutyraldehyde in racemic form as identified by chiral GC. The same experiment was repeated employing **C2**, which does not require preliminary oxidative activation. A 20:80 enantiomeric mixture was observed, revealing the role of the additive in the enolization of the chiral aldehyde. This last finding is in line with the previously observed decrease in stereoselectivity (*vide supra*) and ¹H NMR data.

Scheme 6: The plausible mechanisms of iron-catalysed: **(A)** amination of alcohols with α -chiral amines; **(B)** *N*-alkylation of amines with chiral β -branched primary alcohols.

Additionally, the effect of the molecular sieves on enantiomeric excess of the target amine was investigated. The reaction between (*R*)-PEA (**2a**) and *n*-pentanol (**1a**) with/without the addition of molecular sieves furnished the mono-alkylated product with high enantiopurity (99% ee) in both cases, whereas the

addition of the molecular sieves to the reaction between *p*-anisidine (**6a**) and (*S*)-2-methylbutanol (**1b**) caused major racemization. Molecular sieves have previously shown to result in epimerization in other reactions^[14c]. The alkylation of **6a** with **1b** was also monitored in time in presence/absence of molecular sieves (Supplementary Figure 1) revealing significant loss of chirality (37% *ee*) already after 6 h reaction time in the presence of molecular sieves, while minor racemization occurred without additive. This could be explained by enolization of the configurationally labile intermediate chiral aldehyde, subsequently leading to the loss of stereochemical integrity in the final amine product.

Conclusion

In summary, we developed a general Fe-catalysed method for the synthesis of enantiopure *N*-alkylated amines starting from commercially available α -chiral amines or β -chiral branched alcohols in the presence of iron-based catalyst *via* the ‘hydrogen borrowing’ strategy. The described protocol was used for the synthesis of *N*-heterocycles, employing biomass-derived diols and applied for the synthesis of known optically pure pharmaceuticals (Fendiline, Cinacalcet). Notably, complete retention of stereochemistry in the amine product was seen when starting with α -chiral amines, whereas racemization, especially in the presence of molecular sieves, occurred when using β -chiral alcohols as substrates. The extent of racemization was influenced by the type of alcohol, as observed in previous studies by Donohoe with iridium catalysis, but could be controlled by the choice of appropriate reaction conditions, especially by use of the acetonitrile complex **C2** as catalyst, that does not require any activator and by avoiding molecular sieves. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first general Fe-catalysed method that allows constructing a wide variety of α - and β -substituted enantioenriched higher amines by one-step coupling of available alcohols and amines, starting from at least one chiral substrate.

Experimental Section

General procedure for the iron-catalyzed *N*-alkylation of amines with alcohols: An oven-dried 20 mL Schlenk tube, equipped with a stirring bar, was charged with the cyclopentadienone iron complex **C1** (0.03 mmol, 6 mol%) and Me₃NO (0.03 mmol, 6 mol%) or **C2** (0.03 mmol, 6 mol%). The Schlenk tube was evacuated and backfilled with argon for three times, then the amine (0.5 mmol), alcohol (4 equivalent, unless otherwise stated in the manuscript) and degassed toluene (2 mL) were sequentially added. The mixture was stirred at 135 °C (temperature of the oil bath) for the indicated time (typically 24 h) and then cooled down to room temperature. The solution was filtered over celite and analyzed by gas chromatography to determine the conversion of the starting amine. The product was isolated by column chromatography on silica gel with pentane/ethyl acetate as eluent mixture and the enantiomeric excess of the amine product was determined by either chiral GC or HPLC (see details for each compound in the SI).

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the People Programme (Marie Curie Actions) of the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme FP7/2007–2013/ under REA grant agreement no. 622724 (Asymm.Fe.Sus.Cat). K.B. is also grateful for financial support from the European Research Council, ERC Starting Grant 2015 (CataSus) 638076. This work is part of the research programme Talent Scheme (Vidi) with Project Number 723.015.005, which is partly financed by The Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO).

References

- [1] a) S. A. Lawrence, Ed., *Amines: Synthesis, Properties and Applications*, Cambridge University Press, **2005**; b) T. C. Nugent, Ed., *Chiral Amine Synthesis: Methods, Developments and Applications*, Wiley-VCH: Weinheim, Germany, **2010**.
 - [2] a) S. Bähn, S. Imm, L. Neubert, M. Zhang, H. Neumann, M. Beller, *ChemCatChem* **2011**, *3*, 1853–1864; b) A. Corma, J. Navas, M. J. Sabater, *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 1410–1459; c) B. G. Reed-Berendt, D. E. Latham, M. B. Dambatta, L. C. Morrill, *ACS Cent. Sci.* **2021**, 10.1021/acscentsci.1c00125.
 - [3] a) K. Barta, P. C. Ford, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2014**, *47*, 1503–1512; b) Z. Sun, G. Bottari, A. Afanasenko, M. C. A. Stuart, P. J. Deuss, B. Fridrich, K. Barta, *Nat. Catal.* **2018**, *1*, 82–92; c) Z. Sun, K. Barta, *Chem. Commun.* **2018**, *54*, 7725–7745.
 - [4] a) R. Kempe, F. Kallmeier, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57*, 46–60; b) T. Irrgang, R. Kempe, *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 1410–1459; c) B. G. Reed-Berendt, K. Polidano, L. C. Morrill, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2018**, *17*, 1595–1607.
- For representative reviews on iron catalysis, see: a) R. H. Morris, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2009**, *38*, 2282–2291; b) I. Bauer, H.-J. Knölker, *Chem. Rev.* **2015**, *115*, 3170–3387; c) T. Ollevier, H. Keipour, In *Iron Catalysis II*; Bauer, E., Ed.; Springer-Verlag: Berlin, **2015**; Vol. 50, p 259–309; d) J.-L. Renaud, S. Gaillard, *Synthesis* **2016**, *48*, 3659–3683; e) A. Mezzetti, *Isr. J. Chem.* **2017**, *57*, 1090–1105; f) D. Wei, C. Darcel, *Chem. Rev.* **2019**, *119*, 2550–2610.
- [5] a) T. Kwok, O. Hoff, R. J. Armstrong, T. J. Donohoe, *Chem. – A Eur. J.* **2020**, *26*, 12912–12926; b) A. Quintard, J. Rodriguez, *Chem. Commun.* **2016**, *52*, 10456–10473; c) M. Roudier, T. Constantieux, J. Rodriguez, A. Quintard, *Chimia* **2016**, *70*, 97–101; d) A. Quintard, T. Constantieux, J. Rodriguez, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, *52*, 12883–12887.
- For selected examples of iron-catalysed hydrogenation (or transfer hydrogenation) of imines, see: a) S. Zhou, S. Fleischer, K. Junge, M. Beller, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2011**, *50*, 5120–5124; b) S. Fleischer, S. Zhou, S. Werkmeister, K. Junge, M. Beller, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2013**, *19*, 4997–5003; c) D. Brenna, S. Rossi, F. Cozzia, M. Benaglia, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2017**, *15*, 5685–5688; d) S. Zhou, S. Fleischer, K. Junge, S. Das, D. Addis, M. Beller, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2010**, *49*, 8121–8125; e)

- A. A. Mikhailine, M. I. Maishan, R. H. Morris, *Org. Lett.* **2012**, *14*, 4638–4641.
- [6] N. J. Oldenhuis, V. M. Dong, Z. Guan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 12548–12551.
- [7] Y. Zhang, C. S. Lim, D. S. Boon Sim, H. J. Pan, Y. Zhao, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2014**, *53*, 1399–1403.
- [8] L. C. Yang, Y. N. Wang, Y. Zhang, Y. Zhao, *ACS Catal.* **2017**, *7*, 93–97.
- [9] a) K. Sakai, N. Hirayama, R. Tamura, Eds., *Novel Optical Resolution Technologies*, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, **2007**; b) H. Yamamoto, E. M. Carreira, Eds., in *Compr. Chirality 1st Ed.*, Elsevier Ltd., **2012**.
- [10] a) K. I. Fujita, T. Fujii, R. Yamaguchi, *Org. Lett.* **2004**, *6*, 3525–3528; b) L. Miao, S. C. DiMaggio, H. Shu, M. L. Trudell, *Org. Lett.* **2009**, *11*, 1579–1582; c) K. Fujita, T. Fujii, A. Komatsubara, Y. Enoki, R. Yamaguchi, *Heterocycles* **2007**, *74*, 673–682.
- [11] A. C. Maxwell, A. J. A. Watson, M. H. S. A. Hamid, J. M. J. Williams, H. C. Maytum, G. W. Lamb, C. L. Allen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *40*, 1766–1774.
- [12] T. Yan, B. L. Feringa, K. Barta, *Sci. Adv.* **2017**, *3*, eaao6494.
- [13] L. Homberg, A. Roller, K. C. Hultsch, *Org. Lett.* **2019**, *21*, 3142–3147.
- [14] a) I. Cumpstey, S. Agrawal, K. E. Borbas, B. Martín-Matute, *Chem. Commun.* **2011**, *47*, 7827–7829; b) K. Zhao, G. Zhou, H. Nie, W. Chen, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2016**, *14*, 9466–9471; c) M. Jacolot, S. Moebs-Sanchez, F. Popowycz, *J. Org. Chem.* **2018**, *83*, 9456–9463; d) A. E. R. Chamberlain, K. J. Paterson, R. J. Armstrong, H. C. Twin, T. J. Donohoe, *Chem. Commun.* **2020**, *56*, 3563–3566.
- [15] T. Yan, B. L. Feringa, K. Barta, *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 5602.
- [16] H. J. Pan, T. W. Ng, Y. Zhao, *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51*, 11907–11910.
- [17] a) K. I. Fujita, W. Ito, R. Yamaguchi, *ChemCatChem* **2014**, *6*, 109–112; b) M. Peña-López, H. Neumann, M. Beller, *ChemCatChem* **2015**, *7*, 865–871; c) M. Yoshida, H. Wang, T. Shimbayashi, K. I. Fujita, *Catalysts* **2018**, *8*, 312–324.
- [18] V. N. Wakchaure, P. S. J. Kaib, M. Leutzsch, B. List, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 11852–11856.
- [19] R. Bayer, R. Mannhold, *Pharmatherapeutica* **1987**, *5*, 103–136.
- [20] X. Tan, S. Gao, W. Zeng, S. Xin, Q. Yin, X. Zhang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2018**, *140*, 2024–2027.
- [21] T. S. Claudino, J. D. Scholten, A. L. Monteiro, *Catal. Commun.* **2017**, *102*, 53–56.
- [22] M. Barniol-Xicota, R. Leiva, C. Escolano, S. Vázquez, *Synthesis* **2016**, *48*, 783–803.
- [23] R. Vlasakova, J. Hajicek, **2013**, PCT Int. Appl. WO2013075679; *Chem. Abstr.* **2013**, *159*, 42445.
- [24] a) O. Verho, J. E. Bäckvall, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 3996–4009; b) K. Adriaensen, J. Vercammen, C. Van Goethem, S. Eyley, I. Vankelecom, W. Thielemans, D. De Vos, *Green Chem.* **2020**, *22*, 85–93.
- [25] a) D. Strübing, P. Krumlinde, J. Piera, J. E. Bäckvall, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2007**, *349*, 1577–1581; b) M. R. Atuu, M. M. Hossain, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2007**, *48*, 3875–3878.
- [26] J. M. Hoover, S. S. Stahl, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 16901–16910.

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